

Understanding the challenges and requirements for facilitating iStar learning: a case study with iStar beginners

Supplemental material

I. EXTRA INFORMATION ABOUT CASE STUDY

We perform participant selection according to our protocol to search for iStar beginners as the participants. To check the experience of these participants, we collect their software development experience via a questionnaire and check their software projects for confirmation.

Table II shows the results of our questionnaire, which contains information about the software developed by beginners, including the developing time, the running time, the lines of code, the requirements fulfillment status, and the user size.

We perform the iStar tutorial and modeling session for iStar beginners and record corresponding results based on protocol. Table I shows the tutorial and modeling results of the beginners.

As planned, iStar models' requirements are consistent with the software they developed. The tutorial and modeling session can help beginners provide more credible and helpful information for the following interview. In the modeling session, beginners' modeling time ranges from 20 to 90 minutes, with an average of 46 minutes spent on modeling. The largest model contains 91 elements, the smallest contains 10, and the average is 47. After they finish modeling, we check and correct the syntax errors to make them learn from their mistakes.

TABLE I
MODELING RESULTS FROM BEGINNERS

ID	Time spent (in minutes)		Number of model elements				
	Tutorial	Modeling	Actors	Intentions	R.	D.	SUM
B1	20	50	4	20	21	8	53
B2	26	90	4	42	33	12	91
B3	26	65	4	30	20	10	64
B4	25	90	3	16	11	3	33
B5	23	20	2	11	9	2	24
B6	22	45	2	15	13	1	31
B7	25	34	2	33	28	2	65
B8	23	25	1	5	4	0	10
B9	24	30	2	37	31	0	70
B10	26	14	1	13	10	0	24
Mean	24	46.3	2.5	22.2	18	3.8	46.5

ID = Participant code, B = Beginner, R. = Refinements, D. = Dependencies

During the interview session, the average time spent with participants is 58 minutes. All interviews with beginners took up to 50 minutes, longer than the average time spent with lecturers, which is 48 minutes.

II. MODELING RESULTS FROM BEGINNERS

The average time spent on the tutorial sessions was 24 minutes. We used the same material to introduce each beginner to the iStar modeling framework. One of the authors gave the tutorial to each beginner to ensure consistency. After the tutorial, beginners could ask any questions they had, and we answered them until they felt they completely understood. The difference in time spent on the tutorial session comes from the Q&A activity.

B8 built the smallest model, and B10 took the shortest modeling time. The online judge platform developed by B2 and B3 was the most complex software system in this case study. Thus, the iStar model constructed by these two participants had the most model elements. Specifically, although B2 and B3 developed the software system together, they participated in our case study separately. B2 took 30 minutes longer to model than B3, with a finer granularity of the actors' intentions in their scenario leading to more intentional elements and refinements. That is why the final model that B2 built contains more elements than B3.

Refinements between intentional elements were most commonly used in the models finalized by beginners. The number of intentional elements reflecting the goals, tasks, and required resources of actors and the number of refinements were the highest model elements in each beginner's model. In the models from beginners, there were about three actors. The dependencies between actors ranged from zero to twelve, with an average of four dependencies. It is worth noting that all the beginners did not use is-a or participates-in relationships between actors during modeling. One possible reason is that they can complete the requirements modeling around several specific roles (e.g., teacher, student). There is no need to use the participants-in relationship to associate these roles with a specific individual.

III. QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ISTAR BEGINNERS

- 1) Please write down your name.
- 2) Describe the functionality of the software project for which you are the lead developer in one sentence.
- 3) You developed this project over a period of time of:
 - A. Less than a month
 - B. More than a month, but less than a quarter

TABLE II
SOFTWARE DEVELOPED BY ISTAR BEGINNERS

ID	Developed software	Developing time	Lines of code	Tech stack	Iterations	Running time	User scale	Requirements satisfaction
B1	An online modeling platform for teaching software engineering	One year	Near 5000	Frontend: ejs Backend: Express, Node.js	Keep iterating	Two years	Near 200	Completely satisfied
B2	An online judge system for teaching data structures	One year	Over 10000	Echo and Go	Major version with bug fixes	Two years	Near 300	Completely satisfied
B3	Developed the online judge system with B2	One year	Over 10000	Frontend: Vue.js Backend: Echo, Go	Keep iterating	Two years	Near 300	Completely satisfied
B4	A serious game for teaching requirements analysis	Three months	Near 1000	Unity 3D, C#	Keep iterating	One year	Near 100	Moderately satisfied
B5	A web application providing information on campus life	One year	Over 10000	Webview miniprogram Python	Keep iterating	Two years	Near 400	Completely satisfied
B6	A map application with Beijing's monuments, museums, and attractions	Three months	Near 5000	Frontend: Vue.js Backend: Spring boot	Keep iterating	Half year	Near 100	Moderately satisfied
B7	An frontend UI for social engineering attacks detection system	Half year	Near 5000	React	Keep iterating	One year	Near 100	Moderately satisfied
B8	An automatic generation system of social engineering attack defense strategy	Half year	Near 5000	Java, Spring boot	Major version with bug fixes	One year	Near 100	Moderately satisfied
B9	An ordering and delivery application for campus	One month	Near 1000	Python Express, Node.js	Only iterative bug fixes	Half year	Near 100	Moderately satisfied
B10	An anomaly modeling behavior detection platform	One month	Near 1000	Qt, Python	Major version with bug fixes	Half year	Near 100	Moderately satisfied

ID = Participant code, B = Beginner

- C. More than a quarter, but less than half a year
D. More than half a year, but less than a year
E. More than a year
- 4) In addition to automatically generated code (such as boilerplate code), the estimated number of lines of code you write while developing this project are:
A. Less than 1000
B. 1000~5000
C. 5000~10000
D. More than 10000
- 5) Please describe the programming language and tech stack used to develop the project.
- 6) Do you do continuous iterations during the development process?
A. No, I just finished the software in one go
B. Partially, I finish the core functionality of the software in one go and have a few bug fixes after that
C. Yes, I finished the development of the software in some iterations and fixed some bugs after the completion without developing new functionalities
D. Yes, I keep iterating to develop the software, including new functionalities and bug fixes
- 7) How long has this project you developed been up and running?
A. Less than half a year
B. More than half a year but less than a year
C. More than a year but less than two years
D. More than two years
- 8) How many users have already used this software you developed?
A. Less than 100
B. 100~200
C. 200~300
D. 300~400
E. More than 400
- 9) To what extent is your software project meeting the requirements of the users?
A. Not at all satisfied
B. Slightly satisfied
C. Moderately satisfied
D. Very satisfied
E. Completely satisfied